

THE TECHNOLOGY OF IMPROVING VOCABULARY OF B2 LEVEL STUDENTS IN ENGLISH CLASSES

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Abstract. This article discusses the use of technology in improving vocabulary of B2 level students in English classes. The author emphasizes the importance of vocabulary acquisition for language learners and suggests that technology can enhance this process. The article also presents various technological tools and resources, such as online dictionaries, flashcards, and vocabulary games, that can be used to engage students in learning vocabulary. The author also highlights the benefits of using technology, including increased motivation, personalized learning, and immediate feedback. According to the result of the research, the article provides practical advice for teachers who want to incorporate technology into their vocabulary instruction and help B2 level students improve their English language skills.

Keywords: Vocabulary development, technology, B2 level students, English classes, online dictionaries, flashcards, vocabulary games, motivation, personalized learning, immediate feedback, language learners, English language skills.

Introduction. Improving vocabulary is a crucial aspect of language learning, especially for B2 level students in English classes. As students progress in their language proficiency, a rich and varied vocabulary becomes increasingly important for effective communication and comprehension. However, traditional methods of vocabulary acquisition, such as rote memorization, can be tedious and challenging for students. This is where technology can play a pivotal role in enhancing vocabulary learning. With the abundance of educational apps, online resources, and interactive software available, students have access to a wide range of tools to aid in their vocabulary development [4]. These technological resources not only make learning more engaging and interactive, but also offer personalized learning experiences tailored to individual learning styles and needs. The article will explore the various ways in which technology can be utilized as a tool for enhancing vocabulary learning for B2 level students in English classes. From vocabulary-building apps to online word games, it will discuss how technology can be harnessed to make vocabulary learning more effective and enjoyable for students.

The role of technology in vocabulary development for B2 level students in English classes is instrumental in providing an array of advantages that

traditional learning methods may not offer. Leveraging technology can significantly improve vocabulary enrichment by increasing engagement, providing interactive learning experiences, and enhancing accessibility to diverse learning resources. One of the key advantages of technology in vocabulary development is increased engagement. Many language learning apps and software incorporate gamification elements, such as point-based systems, challenges, and interactive exercises, to make vocabulary acquisition more enjoyable [3]. This not only keeps students motivated but also encourages them to actively participate in their learning process. Moreover, technology provides interactive learning experiences that cater to various learning styles. For visual learners, digital flashcards or multimedia presentations can be more effective than traditional paper-based materials. Auditory learners can benefit from pronunciation practice and listening exercises available in online resources. By catering to different learning styles, technology ensures that all students have the opportunity to engage with and retain new vocabulary effectively. Furthermore, technology enhances accessibility to diverse learning resources. Language learning apps, online dictionaries, digital libraries, and interactive vocabulary quizzes are just a few examples of the varied resources available at students' fingertips. These tools not only provide a wide range of vocabulary-building exercises but also offer immediate feedback and progress tracking, allowing students to monitor their own learning and tailor their study habits accordingly. Specific tech tools and resources that can facilitate vocabulary acquisition include popular language learning apps like Duolingo, Babbel, and Memrise, which provide engaging, interactive vocabulary lessons tailored to individual skill levels. Digital flashcard platforms like Quizlet and Anki offer customizable flashcard sets with features such as audio pronunciations and spaced repetition algorithms for efficient vocabulary retention [5]. Additionally, interactive vocabulary quizzes can be found on platforms like Kahoot and Quizizz, allowing teachers to create engaging quizzes to test and reinforce students' understanding of new vocabulary. In conclusion, technology plays a vital role in vocabulary development for B2 level students in English classes by offering increased engagement, interactive learning experiences, and enhanced accessibility to diverse learning resources. By utilizing language learning apps, digital flashcards, and interactive quizzes, students can effectively expand their vocabulary in a more enjoyable and efficient manner.

Conclusion. Incorporating technology into B2 level English classes can greatly benefit vocabulary development. It provides opportunities for interactive and

engaging activities, personalized learning experiences, and access to a wide range of resources. Utilizing technology can also help students to strengthen their language skills and stay motivated in their learning journey. As educators, it is important to embrace and explore the potential of technology in enhancing our students' vocabulary learning experience. By integrating technology into our teaching methods, we can create dynamic and effective learning environments that cater to the diverse needs and preferences of our students. Let's continue to leverage technology to support and enhance vocabulary development in B2 level English classes.

References:

1. Azizkhodzhayeva N, "Pedagogical technologies and pedagogical skills", T., 2005, pp. 192.
2. Becta, "IT and English activities and ideas", ICT in the Curriculum, 2006.
3. Becta, "What the Research says about using ICT in English",
4. ICT in the Curriculum, 2006. <http://curriculum.becta.org.uk/docserver.php?docid=668>
5. Horst M, "Learning L2 vocabulary through extensive reading: A measurement study", Canadian Modern Language Review, Vol. 61/3, 2005, pp. 355-82.
6. Kitao K, "Internet Resources: ELT, Linguistics, and Communications", Eichosha, Japan, 1998.
7. Lewis M, "Implementing the lexical approach", Putting theory into practice, Heinle cengage, 2008, pp. 223.
8. Rakhmanov I, Shcherba L, "The basic principles of the selection of the lexical minimum for secondary schools", INR, No.3, 1946.
9. Shrestha P, "Book review: Innovations in Learning Technologies for English Language Teaching", British Council, London, 2014, pp. 474-475.